

1 Highlights

- 2 • Genetic variance is important to estimate future genetic progress
- 3 • Selection and drift reduce genetic variance
- 4 • In Manech Tête Rousse the loss of genetic variance was about 13% for females
- 5 • Bulmer effect had more impact (10%) than drift (3%)
- 6 • Changes in breeding objectives affect the evolution of genetic variance

7

8 **Selection and drift reduce genetic variation for milk yield in**

9 **Manech Tête Rousse dairy sheep.**

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23 **Abstract**

24 Decreases in genetic variance over generations reduce future genetic gain. We studied the evolution
25 of genetic variance in the dairy sheep breed Manech Tête Rousse, which has been selected for
26 increasingly complex objectives including in this order: milk yield, milk contents, scrapie resistance
27 and somatic cell score. We estimated base population genetic variance and genetic variance per sex
28 and per year of birth from 1981 until 2014. The data consisted on 1,842,295 records of milk yield
29 (from 1978 to 2017) and a pedigree including 530,572 females (96% of them with records) and 3,798
30 Artificial Insemination males. As a measure of drift, we computed average relationships for each
31 cohort from which we derived expected reduction of variance due to increased relationships. The
32 difference between observed and expected reductions of genetic variances is the reduction in genetic
33 variance due to selection.

34 Average relationships increased steadily but slowly in both sexes. For females, genetic variance
35 reduced along the years until a plateau was reached around 90% of the initial genetic variance. The
36 reduction due to relationships (roughly 3% cumulated in 30 years) was smaller than the reduction due
37 to selection (roughly 10% across the last years). Smaller loss due due to selection was seen in recent
38 years, possibly due to a change in selection objectives. These results agree well with theoretical
39 expectations. The pattern of the evolution of genetic variance in males is similar to the one for
40 females, but with a stronger reduction, because of strong selection of AI males at birth.

41 We conclude that the reductions of genetic variation due to selection and drift agree with expectations
42 and none of the reductions are very strong in this population, due to control of inbreeding and smooth
43 change in selection objectives during the years.

44

45 **Main body**

46 There are two processes in the evolution of genetic variance under artificial selection. First, there is
47 an effect of limited population size, by which the buildup of coancestry (half the relationship

48 coefficient) reduces genetic variation as animals become increasingly related. This reduction is well
49 known and can be understood as drift (Sorensen and Kennedy, 1984; Falconer and Mackay, 1996). It
50 acts independently of selection, i.e. it is only due to demographic factors and is the same for all traits.
51 Second, selection causes directed changes in allele frequencies and negative linkage disequilibrium
52 (LD) among quantitative trait loci (QTL), also known as Bulmer effect. In an infinitesimal model and
53 in the short term, the reduction of genetic variance is due mostly to negative covariance between
54 QTL, while directed changes in allele frequencies have a small impact (Bulmer, 1971; Walsh and
55 Lynch, 2018). However, the reduction of genetic variation due to LD is not constant, with a significant
56 reduction until the 3rd or 4th generation, when it becomes stable as there is an equilibrium between
57 recombination and LD (Dekkers, 1992; Villanueva et al., 1993). Typical values of reduction of
58 genetic variance due to the Bulmer effect, until its stability, range in the 5%-20%. Genetic variance
59 of the unselected population is “genetic” variance, whereas genetic variance of the population at hand
60 for selection (eventually, after reduction due to selection) is “genetic” variance (Walsh and Lynch,
61 2018).

62 Reduction of genetic variance affects genetic gain and its prediction. The genetic gain is often
63 predicted based on base population parameters, without taking account of the Bulmer effect. The
64 reduction in genetic variance also decreases heritability, thus affecting accuracy of selection (Bulmer,
65 1971; Dekkers, 1992; Bijma, 2012; Gorjanc et al., 2015). The Bulmer effect is well understood in
66 simplified contexts based on selection index theory (Dekkers, 1992; Villanueva et al., 1993; Rutten
67 et al., 2002). Villanueva et al. (1993) quantified that between 8% and 26% of the reduction in the
68 response of multivariate BLUP selection was due to the Bulmer effect.

69 Recent introduction of genomic selection has renewed interest in the Bulmer effect (van Grevenhof
70 et al., 2012; Gorjanc et al., 2015; Allier et al., 2019; Hidalgo et al., 2020). van Grevenhof et al. (2012)
71 showed by deterministic simulations that the decrease in the genetic gain is the same for genomic

72 selection and for traditional BLUP selection. However, there are very few estimates based on actual
73 records of reduction of genetic variance in selected populations. Allier et al. (2019) estimated that the
74 Bulmer effect accounted for a 23% reduction of the genetic variance. They compared the genetic
75 variance in the existing selected population of maize, which is in LD, to the genetic variance in a
76 hypothetical population in linkage equilibrium. However, in their study there is no base population
77 in a pedigree sense, i.e. an ancestral, unselected population. Hidalgo et al. (2020) reported substantial
78 reductions of genetic variance in a pig population selected for growth and fitness traits. However,
79 none of these authors decomposed the reduction in genetic variance into the loss of genetic diversity
80 due to drift (i.e. the buildup of coancestry among individuals) and the Bulmer effect (i.e. the buildup
81 of LD across QTL). It is of interest to disentangle these two phenomena, in order to prepare optimal
82 strategies for long-term breeding – for instance, the Bulmer effect is smaller when the selection
83 objective changes or when the next generation is produced by mating at random, whereas the loss due
84 to coancestry can potentially be handled by strategies such as Optimal Contribution Selection
85 (Woolliams et al., 2015).

86 Dairy sheep is an interesting species to study the Bulmer effect. In France, the cooperative schemes
87 have strategies at the breed level to handle inbreeding. Also, these schemes have clearly defined and
88 consensual selection objectives at each time period. This is opposite to dairy cattle where different
89 AI studs may propose different portfolios of bulls, and breeding objectives and strategies may differ
90 among actors. Also, in dairy sheep the populations are big enough (in the tens of thousands of animals
91 born yearly) for accurate inferences of the evolution of Bulmer effect. The objective of this work was
92 to estimate the trajectory of genetic variance over years, and the reduction of genetic variance due to
93 coancestry and Bulmer effect, for the trait yearly milk yield in Manech Tête Rousse sheep, a breed
94 that extensively uses AI (more than 70% of replacement females are born from AI).

95 **Data.** We used all available milk yield records (from 1978 to 2017) and pedigree of Manech Tête
96 Rouse (MTR) (roughly with the same time span as the milk records). That means 1,842,295 records
97 of milk yield and 540,999 individuals in the pedigree (530,572 females among which 96%
98 have records, and 3,798 Artificial Insemination males). The average generation interval was roughly
99 4 years, so there are ~10 generations. There is no formal use of Optimal Contribution Selection in
100 this population, but matings among cousins are avoided, so recent inbreeding is avoided. Data was
101 pre-corrected for heterogeneity of variances using the method of Meuwissen et al. (1996) to avoid
102 scale effects. Breeding objectives in Manech Tête Rouse are relevant for interpretation of the results.
103 From the start of the breeding program in the 80's until 2003, the only objective was milk yield per
104 annual lactation. From 2003 until 2016, the breeding objective was fat and protein yields (genetically
105 highly correlated with milk yield) and this gradually changed to fat and protein contents, to avoid
106 deterioration of cheese-making (Barillet, 1997). From 2016 somatic cell score was added. From 2000
107 to 2005 there was also an emphasis in selecting scrapie-resistant rams (Palhiere et al., 2008), which
108 partially diminished selection pressure on other traits.

109 **Model.** Genetic evaluation was by pedigree BLUP animal model with permanent environment effect
110 to account for repeated measurements. The linear model included contemporary group (flock, year
111 and lactation number), age, lactation number, month of lambing and interval lambing to first milk
112 recording. Random effects were animal and permanent environment. As there are approximately 20%
113 missing sires in the pedigree, the model included 13 Unknown Parent Groups every 3 years.

114 **Method.** We follow the method presented in Sorensen et al. (2001). We focus on the evolution of
115 male (AI rams) and female (commercial females at farms) genetic variances along time, although the
116 method is very general and it can be applied for any partition of animals of interest. We used Gibbs
117 sampling with 150,000 iterations, a burn in of 15,000 and saving samples each 150 iterations. We
118 obtained the posterior distribution of the genetic variance at the base population, σ_a^2 . Also, at each

119 150-th iteration we took samples of EBVs for groups of individuals formed by sex (males and
120 females) and year of birth year t (1981 to 2014). We computed the variance of the samples of EBV's
121 for each of these $34 \times 2 = 68$ groups. These variances are, in turn, samples from the posterior
122 distributions of genetic variances of males at time t ($\sigma_{a(m)}^{2(t)}$) and genetic variance of females at time t
123 ($\sigma_{a(f)}^{2(t)}$). So, at the end of the process we had the posterior distribution (with 900 samples) of the
124 genetic variance for each of the 34 groups of AI males $\hat{\sigma}_{a(m)}^{2(t)}$ and each of the 34 groups of females
125 $\hat{\sigma}_{a(f)}^{2(t)}$, and of the genetic variance in the base population ($\hat{\sigma}_a^2$).

126 **Reduction of genetic variance due to the increase of average inbreeding and relationship.** The
127 expected genetic variance as a function of average inbreeding (\bar{F}_t) and average relationship ($\bar{\mathbf{A}}_t$ where
128 \mathbf{A}_t is the corresponding submatrix of additive relationships) of animals born at time t is $E\left(\sigma_a^{2(t)}\right) =$
129 $\sigma_a^2 \left(\overline{\text{diag}(\mathbf{A}_t)} - \bar{\mathbf{A}}_t\right) = \sigma_a^2(1 + \bar{F}_t - \bar{\mathbf{A}}_t)$ (Sorensen et al., 2001; Legarra, 2016). This expression
130 takes into account that animals at time t are inbred (which increases the variance) and related (which
131 decreases the variance). The reasoning extends to separate sexes by computing separate averages \bar{F}_t
132 and $\bar{\mathbf{A}}_t$. Relationships and inbreeding were obtained using INBUPGF90 (Aguilar and Misztal, 2008).

133 **Reduction of genetic variance due to selection.** The difference between the observed genetic
134 variance $\hat{\sigma}_a^{2(t)}$ and expected genetic variance $E\left(\sigma_a^{2(t)}\right)$ is considered to be reduction of genetic
135 variance due to selection. This includes both Bulmer effect but also pre-selection of animals at birth
136 based on Parent Average. The pre-selection is strong in males but mild in females. We will assume
137 that the genetic variance in females is representative of the population. The expected reduction due
138 to increased relationships is $\sigma_a^2 - \sigma_a^2(1 + \bar{F}_t - \bar{\mathbf{A}}_t) = \sigma_a^2(-\bar{F}_t + \bar{\mathbf{A}}_t)$. The observed reduction in
139 genetic variance is $\sigma_a^2 - \hat{\sigma}_a^{2(t)}$. Thus the reduction due to Bulmer and pre-selection is $\left(\sigma_a^2 - \hat{\sigma}_a^{2(t)}\right) -$
140 $\left(\sigma_a^2 - \sigma_a^2(1 + \bar{F}_t - \bar{\mathbf{A}}_t)\right) = \sigma_a^2(1 + \bar{F}_t - \bar{\mathbf{A}}_t) - \hat{\sigma}_a^{2(t)}$, the expected minus the observed genetic

141 variance. Again, the reasoning extends easily to separate sexes. For example, if σ_a^2 in the base
142 population is 100, and $1 + \bar{F}_{f,2000} - \bar{A}_{f,2000} = 0.9$, the expected genetic variance in females at year
143 2000 is $\sigma_a^2(1 + \bar{F}_{f,2000} - \bar{A}_{f,2000}) = 90$. If estimated $\hat{\sigma}_{a(f)}^{2(2000)}$ is 75, the loss due to Bulmer effect
144 and pre-selection is $90 - 75 = 15$.

145 **Theoretical calculation of genetic variance at equilibrium.** The genetic variance at equilibrium
146 was calculated using the program SelAction 2.2 (Rutten et al., 2002) modelling a selection scheme
147 similar to the actual one, based on progeny test for males, own phenotype for females and parent
148 average for young animals. We assumed two breeding objectives (milk yield alone or milk yield,
149 composition and somatic cell score), corresponding to the change along the years of breeding
150 objectives, and three heritabilities of 0.20, 0.25 and 0.30 around the estimated heritability of 0.28.

151

152 **Results.** The estimated genetic variance at the base population for milk yield was (\pm s.e., in liters
153 squared, L²) 499.2 ± 5.2 , permanent environmental variance was 409.3 ± 3.6 and the residual variance
154 was 857.3 ± 1.2 . The estimated h^2 was 0.28 ± 0.003 . This h^2 value is very similar to a previous estimate
155 (Legarra et al., 2014).

156 In Figure 1 we present the evolution of overall relationship coefficient (twice the coancestry). There
157 was a fast increase of coancestry for AI males at the beginning of the breeding scheme, followed by
158 a steady trend of about 0.002 increase per year. There is a steady increase of female-female and
159 female-AI males coancestries. Trends for inbreeding are similar. Thus, a small reduction in the
160 genetic variance resulting from drift is expected.

161

162 **Figure 1.**

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164

165 **Figure 2.**

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168 **Figure 3.**

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170 In Figure 2 and Figure 3 we present, for females and AI males respectively, the genetic variance
171 trajectory and the reduction of genetic variance due to drift and selection (Bulmer effect plus pre-
172 selection at birth for AI males). For females, the lowest value of genetic variance was $438.6 \pm 5.6 L^2$
173 in 2007 and after 2011 the curve started to increase. For AI males, the genetic variance reached the
174 lowest value ($282.5 \pm 19.9 L^2$) in 2008 and increased in the following years, as for females. The
175 reduction in genetic variance for AI males is stronger than the one for females. As mentioned
176 previously, the trend for males includes not only reduction due to drift and Bulmer effect, but also
177 (and importantly), reduction due to strong pre-selection of males at birth based on Parent Average
178 EBV. On the contrary, in the female population there is very little pre-selection pressure at birth.
179 The increase in coancestry explains only a small proportion of the reduction of genetic variance in
180 MTR, whereas the remaining is attributable to the Bulmer effect (in females) and to Bulmer effect
181 and selection at birth (in AI males). The reduction due to the Bulmer effect (and selection) seems to
182 stabilize in the last decade. However, it is not possible to say if this plateau is due to the stabilization
183 of Bulmer effect (as predicted by the theory) or due to changes in the breeding objective (as happens
184 in this breeding scheme).

185 Finally, the results for the theoretical reduction in genetic variance computed with SelAction are as
186 follows. A scheme selecting for milk yield (breeding objective at the beginning of the scheme) has,
187 at equilibrium, a 15% reduction due to Bulmer effect, whereas a scheme selecting for milk yield,
188 composition and somatic cell score has an 8% loss for milk yield. These numbers agree with our

189 estimations of roughly, a 10% of loss due to Bulmer effect in females. The cumulated loss due to
190 increased coancestry is roughly 3% in both cases.

191 Our results have interest on their own. To our knowledge, there are few estimates of the reduction of
192 genetic variance with real data (Allier et al., 2019; Hidalgo et al., 2020), and none of them
193 disentangles the effect of drift from the effect of selection. What we observe is that the reduction due
194 to drift is small, in spite of popular concerns on the increase of inbreeding. The reduction due to
195 selection is larger, but it dissipates with the change in selection objectives. This suggests that a
196 breeding scheme with mild control of effective population size, coupled with changes in breeding
197 objectives, should be enough to avoid important loss of genetic variability.

198

199 **Conclusion.** For milk yield in Manech Tête Rousse dairy sheep, there has been a steady reduction of
200 genetic variance due to drift (roughly 3% in 30 years) and reduction due to selection (roughly 10% in
201 30 years). The loss due to selection reached an asymptotic value due to either the nature of the Bulmer
202 effect or the change of selection objectives. These results highlight that there is a need to check the
203 evolution of genetic variability and that common strategies diversifying selection objectives and
204 reducing increase of inbreeding result in small losses of genetic variation.

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206 **References**

207 Aguilar, I., and I. Misztal. 2008. Technical note: Recursive algorithm for inbreeding coefficients
208 assuming nonzero inbreeding of unknown parents. *J. Dairy Sci.* 91:1669–1672.
209 doi:10.3168/jds.2007-0575.

210 Allier, A., S. Teyssèdre, C. Lehermeier, B. Claustres, S. Maltese, S. Melkior, L. Moreau, and A.
211 Charcosset. 2019. Assessment of breeding programs sustainability: application of phenotypic

212 and genomic indicators to a North European grain maize program. *Theor. Appl. Genet.*
213 132:1321–1334. doi:10.1007/s00122-019-03280-w.

214 Barillet, F. 1997. *Genetics of milk production. A.* (Eds. . Piper, L., Ruvinsky, ed. CAB
215 International, United Kingdom.

216 Bijma, P. 2012. Accuracies of estimated breeding values from ordinary genetic evaluations do not
217 reflect the correlation between true and estimated breeding values in selected populations. *J.*
218 *Anim. Breed. Genet.* 129:345–358. doi:10.1111/j.1439-0388.2012.00991.x.

219 Bulmer, M.G. 1971. The effect of selection on genetic variability. *Am. Nat.* 105:201–211.

220 Dekkers, J.C.M. 1992. Asymptotic response to selection on best linear unbiased predictors of
221 breeding values. *Anim. Prod.* 54:351–360. doi:10.1017/S0003356100020808.

222 Falconer, D.S., and T.F.C. Mackay. 1996. *Introduction to Quantitative Genetics.* 4th ed. Longmans
223 Green, ed. Harlow, Essex, UK.

224 Gorjanc, G., P. Bijma, and J.M. Hickey. 2015. Reliability of pedigree-based and genomic
225 evaluations in selected populations. *Genet. Sel. Evol.* 47:65. doi:10.1186/s12711-015-0145-1.

226 Van Grevenhof, E.M., J.A. Van Arendonk, and P. Bijma. 2012. Response to genomic selection: The
227 Bulmer effect and the potential of genomic selection when the number of phenotypic records is
228 limiting. *Genet. Sel. Evol.* 44:1–10. doi:10.1186/1297-9686-44-26.

229 Hidalgo, J., S. Tsuruta, D. Lourenco, Y. Masuda, Y. Huang, K.A. Gray, and I. Misztal. 2020.
230 Changes in genetic parameters for fitness and growth traits in pigs under genomic selection. *J.*
231 *Anim. Sci.* 98:1–12. doi:10.1093/jas/skaa032.

232 Legarra, A. 2016. Comparing estimates of genetic variance across different relationship models.
233 *Theor. Popul. Biol.* 107:26–30. doi:10.1016/j.tpb.2015.08.005.

234 Legarra, A., G. Baloche, F. Barillet, J.M. Astruc, C. Soulas, X. Aguerre, F. Arrese, L. Mintegi, M.
235 Lasarte, F. Maeztu, I. Beltrán de Heredia, and E. Ugarte. 2014. Within- and across-breed

236 genomic predictions and genomic relationships for Western Pyrenees dairy sheep breeds
237 Latxa, Manech, and Basco-Béarnaise. *J. Dairy Sci.* 97:3200–3212. doi:10.3168/JDS.2013-
238 7745.

239 Meuwissen, T.H.E., G. De Jong, and B. Engel. 1996. Joint Estimation of Breeding Values and
240 Heterogeneous Variances of Large Data Files. *J. Dairy Sci.* 79:310–316.
241 doi:10.3168/jds.S0022-0302(96)76365-8.

242 Palhiere, I., M. Brochard, K. Moazami-Goudarzi, D. Laloeë, Y. Amigues, B. Bed’hom, E. Neuts, C.
243 Leymarie, T. Pantano, E.P. Cribiu, B. Bibé, and E. Verrier. 2008. Impact of strong selection
244 for the PrP major gene on genetic variability of four French sheep breeds(Open Access
245 publication).. *Genet. Sel. Evol.* 40:663–680. doi:10.1186/1297-9686-40-6-663.

246 Rutten, M.J.M., P. Bijma, J.A. Woolliams, and J.A.M. Van Arendonk. 2002. SelAction: Software to
247 predict selection response and rate of inbreeding in livestock breeding programs. *J. Hered.*
248 93:456–458. doi:10.1093/jhered/93.6.456.

249 Sorensen, D., R. Fernando, and D. Gianola. 2001. Inferring the trajectory of genetic variance in the
250 course of artificial selection. *Genet. Res.* 77:83–94. doi:10.1017/S0016672300004845.

251 Sorensen, D.A., and B.W. Kennedy. 1984. Estimation of Genetic Variances from Unselected and
252 Selected Populations. *J. Anim. Sci.* 59:1213–1223. doi:10.2527/jas1984.5951213x.

253 Villanueva, B., N.R. Wrayh, and R. Thompson. 1993. Prediction of asymptotic rates of response
254 from selection on multiple traits using univariate and multivariate best linear unbiased
255 predictors. *Anim. Prod.* 57:1–13.

256 Walsh, B., and M. Lynch. 2018. *Evolution and Selection of Quantitative Traits*. Oxford University
257 Press, Oxford.

258 Woolliams, J.A., P. Berg, B.S. Dagnachew, and T.H.E. Meuwissen. 2015. Genetic contributions
259 and their optimization. *J. Anim. Breed. Genet.* 132:89–99. doi:10.1111/jbg.12148.

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272 Macedo

273 Figure 1.

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275 **Figure 1.** Evolution of average relationship per year of birth for AI males, females and AI males -

276 females.

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280 Figure 2.

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282 **Figure 2.** Partitioning of the genetic variance along the years for the female population. Red: observed

283 genetic variance. Blue: loss of genetic variance due to drift. Green: loss of genetic variance due to

284 selection.

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287 Figure 3.

288

289 **Figure 3.** Partitioning of the genetic variance along the years for the AI male population. Red:
290 observed genetic variance. Blue: loss of genetic variance due to drift. Green: loss of genetic variance
291 due to selection and pre-selection at birth.

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